

The Role of External Monitoring in Enhancing the Academic Quality in Secondary Schools

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ABSTRACT:

This research aims to investigate the impact of external evaluation and monitoring in enhancing the academic excellence of secondary schools in Punjab and to emphasize the value and advantages of these practices in enhancing academic quality. According to Lodhi, F. A., and Faizi, W. N. (2009:1–11), every member of a nation has the fundamental right to a high-quality education, hence it is regrettable that Pakistan's educational standards are deteriorating as each day of the academic year goes by.

Goal 4 of Sustainable Development Agenda emphasizes providing everyone with access to high-quality, inclusive education for the formation of people and civilizations. It is a challenging task to guarantee that education fulfills the greatest criteria of quality, nevertheless. This is where assessment and monitoring come into play, offering crucial instruments to gauge and raise educational standards. In many nations around the world, Effective and successful system for monitoring and evaluation coupled with a robust accountability mechanism have demonstrated positive outcomes in recent years. Punjab province, established a special academic monitoring body in public schools to raise the standard of instruction by monitoring quality indicators. The study uses both qualitative and quantitative datasets, involving 429 participants from three Punjab regions: Faisalabad, Rahim Yar Khan, and Rawalpindi, to target principals, teachers, and MEAs in 20 public secondary schools. The researcher also discussed the instruments with the supervisor to ascertain their validity. The researcher utilized stratified sampling techniques, using two questionnaires for data collection from heads, teachers, and MEAs, and conducted interviews with CEOs, DEOs, and DMOs, after ensuring validity. Reliability was ensured by calculating the Cronbach coefficient. The study offers valuable insights into the impact of assessment and monitoring on improving academic excellence in secondary schools, aiding policymakers in formulating effective monitoring and evaluation processes. The data, analyzed using SPSS, found that staff inspections have reduced absenteeism among teaching and non-teaching workers, suggesting that school monitoring can enhance education standards. The study suggests reformation of Monitoring, focusing on standard assessments, and teachers' professional training identified by MEAs and MEAs professional training, as staff inspections resulted in reduced absenteeism rates. The absence of essential amenities at the school level was also noted by the researcher. This study's findings could inform the Ministry of Education and other stakeholders about the effectiveness of strategy implementation on academic performance in secondary schools.

The study suggests that the government should invest in employee training on M&E tools, allocate adequate funds, and practice accountability. It also recommends stakeholder involvement in the M&E process, proactive design of M&E systems, and timely guidance. Further research is recommended to assess different thematic areas.

Key Words: External Monitoring and Evaluation, secondary schools, Monitoring and Evaluation Assistants, academic quality, Punjab.

Problem Statement: This study investigates impact of secondary educational institutions monitoring on academic quality improvement in Punjab secondary schools, evaluating its effectiveness in achieving academic excellence.

Objectives: The following were the goals of this study: To

1. Identify the factors affecting the quality of Secondary educational Institutions in Punjab.
2. Analyze impact of School Monitoring on enhancing academic quality of Secondary Schools
3. To recommend certain measures to raise academic quality of Secondary Schools in Punjab.

Research Questions

1. What are the factors affecting the quality of education in Secondary educational Institutions in Punjab?
2. What is the impact of External Monitoring on academic quality of Secondary Schools?
3. What measures can be taken to raise academic quality of Secondary Schools in Punjab?

Study hypothesis:

H0: There is no significant impact of school monitoring practices in enhancing academic quality.

H1: There is a significant impact of school monitoring practices in enhancing academic quality

Rationale for the Research:

Monitoring and evaluation (M&E) has become a crucial instrument for performance management and policy formation, it is necessary to evaluate the effectiveness of M&E systems. While funders and stakeholders require M&E results to assure resource accountability while simultaneously enhancing the programs' overall efficacy, economic policymakers depend on the data produced by M&E functions to better their economic policies (Mackay, 2007).

Significance for Education:

Monitoring and assessment are critical for the achievement or failing of any educational initiative, policy, or program, as they ensure compliance with expectations and results. Monitoring and evaluation are crucial for assessing school performance, identifying cause and effect variables, comparing actual to predicted outcomes, and identifying performance issues and solutions. Monitoring and evaluation of education includes community mobilization efforts, analyzing educational research initiatives, evaluating teacher policies, and building infrastructure projects. These areas focus on incorporating learners, analyzing research results, evaluating professional associations, and assessing teaching methods and applicability.

INTRODUCTION: The main goal of education is to help kids live better lives by providing them with high-quality instruction and learning opportunities, enabling each child to reach their full potential. The Punjab government in Pakistan has established a unique education monitoring authority to improve education quality, aiming to achieve Sustainable Development Goal 4 through comprehensive assessment and analysis. A key component of officer management in guaranteeing high-quality education is effective monitoring (Shah, 2009). Within the Punjab Education System Reforms Programme (PESRP), the Punjab government (2001) implemented reforms in the education system in 2000. In 2001, the Punjab province government established the Programme Monitoring and Implementation Unit (PMIU) to oversee the third pillar of PESRP, aiming to expand educational opportunities, enhancing governance, raising educational standards and promote devolution.

The Punjab government's programs and projects are monitored by the PMIU, with 36 District Monitoring Officers assigned to each of the province's 36 districts. Following recommendations from the province government's services and general administration department, the Chief Minister Secretariat personally nominated these DMOs, who were chosen from the District Management Group. The PMIU created the Monitoring Cell as a sub-department to oversee its

educational programs. Junior Commissioned Officers (JCOs) who had retired from the army were assigned to tour schools and gather statistics. They designated these newly hired field employees as Monitoring and Evaluation Assistants (MEAs). They provide the District Monitoring Officer with their monthly report, which they produce. District Monitoring Officers transmit copies of their monthly reports to the Chief Minister of Punjab and the relevant District Coordinating Officer (DCO). It is the responsibility of the DCO to direct pertinent education officers to take the necessary measures following the DMO report. The Chief Minister receives updates from the DCO regarding their actions. At the district level, both departments are managed by the same person, the DCO. Data from the public education system is captured by the monitoring system and is periodically verified by an outside entity (Government of Punjab, 2001). The data demonstrated that Punjab province has made improvements in the education department via PESRP with the support of monitoring participants (head teachers, DEO, DMO, CEO-EDU, and MEA). PESRP has increased secondary enrollment (Government of Punjab, 2007). These successes are the result of several reasons, including the devolution of authority, internal and external monitoring, government effort and dedication, and media campaigns. Every element is dependent on monitoring as the data and facts supplied by the system enable educational administrators to implement remedial actions. The researcher decided to explore External monitoring systems to determine the influence of external monitoring systems on the academic quality of secondary schools. It's critical to monitor and evaluate for any given project to succeed. They significantly impact the quality of service delivered, especially in education. Organizations responsible for monitoring programs must adopt effective strategies to deliver their mandate efficiently.

This research will aid project managers, donor agencies, and staff in understanding monitoring and evaluation mechanisms to meet stakeholder expectations. It will guide policies for efficient systems and demonstrate accountability and transparency. This research is beneficial for the authorities and policymakers to comprehend the function of exterior observation in uplifting the overall performance of secondary schools. The findings of this research help them to make decisions to meet the demands of quality education and good governance. It is also useful for donor organizations such as the UNESCO and the World Bank. To deliver them with a precise illustration of the conditions. It also helps chief minister's surveillance team and education department by giving them real-time perspectives on the effectiveness of external monitoring.

The lack of research in this area was another factor that motivated the researcher to go into this subject. It appears that no research has been done on the subject at hand or anything related to it. The purpose of this study was to close this gap.

Literature Review:

Concept of Monitoring and Evaluation:

Monitoring is the continuous process of obtaining and assessing information on a programme and evaluating the efficacy of the intervention by comparing expected and actual results. It employs program-generated data (participant characteristics, enrollment and attendance, beneficiaries' post-program circumstances, and programme expenses) to compare participants across persons, programme kinds, and geographic areas. For assessment, a reliable monitoring system needs to be in place.

Evaluation is the procedure of carefully and objectively assessing every part of a programme, including its design, implementation, and results, to determine the overall worth or applicability of the programme. The objective is to provide decision-makers trustworthy data so they can devise plans to achieve more of the desired results.

According to Khan (2012), monitoring is the act of keeping track of modifications to a project, programme, or policy's results throughout time. It involves the regular and methodical gathering of data from policies, initiatives, and programmes to analyze results for input/output purposes, learn from mistakes, and make required adjustments. As a result, it offers two key benefits: (1) internal and external responsibility for the resources utilized and the outcomes achieved; and (2) a foundation for making well-informed decisions about the future of a project. It also adjusts results to suit the goals of the initiative or policy's beneficiaries. This explanation of monitoring has made plain the function of monitoring in a company where supervisory and monitoring responsibilities are common. For learning, change management, and re-modeling/replanning, monitoring during the implementation stages entails the methodical collection, processing, and documentation of outcomes, procedures, and experiences.

On the other side, evaluation seeks to determine and apply the results for new initiatives, policies, or programs by evaluating the linkages between the cause and effect factors. This may be the cause of Okpala, Onocha, and Oyedeji's (1995) definition of evaluation as the act of obtaining reliable data on the accomplishment of learning goals and then evaluating and creating data to support a decision on the efficacy of instruction or a curriculum. When the time comes to decide, evaluation enters the picture. Evaluation is superior to monitoring because it provides policymakers with precise direction.

Assessing the impact of a project, initiative, or policy that has been executed methodically and objectively is therefore part of the evaluation process. Assessment evaluates facts and data on cause-and-effect linkages that are important for better forecasting outcomes and making strategic decisions. Evaluation guarantees, then, that the programme, policy, or project and its variables are assessed for their:

1. Pertinence to anticipated results
2. The ability to effectively address issues found in the process of attaining desired outcomes
3. The effectiveness of the process's resource utilization as well as the program's, project's, or policy's effectiveness in resolving the issues raised
4. Evaluation of the program's, policy's, or plan's impacts
5. The sustainability of the task, policy, or initiative's outcomes

To guarantee better results are obtained, monitoring and evaluation are consequently jointly seen as a methodical process of gathering, processing, and applying information connected to policies, projects, and programs before, during, and after implementation.

Monitoring involves the systematic gathering and examination of data on the utilisation, coverage, and implementation of programs, allowing for timely identification of shortcomings. Evaluation, on the other hand, assesses the relevance, efficiency, and effectiveness of a program, measuring its impact on the standard of living of people. High-quality information in the education sector is essential for monitoring and evaluating program performance, informing policy development, and ensuring effective patient care. The surge in international funding for education emphasizes the need for accurate statistics to track progress and performance, supporting result-based performance and accountability. Timely and reliable data is crucial for decision-making in this context. The production of trustworthy data for monitoring the progress of educational initiatives and fortifying education system is a challenge faced by many developing nations. Since it can be difficult to predict whether a strategy will be successful in a given setting, monitoring information can help strategies be more effective by adjusting them to local conditions.

Relevance to Education: According to Mtetsha (2012), Monitoring and evaluation are crucial for the success or failure of educational programs, projects, and policies, requiring effective planning, implementation, and compliance with expectations and outcomes. The monitoring and evaluation process makes sure that policies are examined to make sure they can offer the best institutional and legal framework for achieving the desired goals. Thus, observing and assessing procedures are pertinent in a variety of educational contexts, including:

1. The monitoring and evaluation procedure makes sure that the policies are examined to make sure they can offer the ideal system of institutions and laws for advancing the anticipated goals.
2. The learners are directly taught by the educational programs. Thus, the outcomes of the educational programs need to be monitored and assessed.
3. Strategies and plans cannot be developed without first determining what needs to be addressed, what has already been tried, and which strategies—all results of policy monitoring and evaluation—work and which don't.
4. The processes of monitoring and evaluation are necessary to determine the variables that influence school performance, compare actual performance to expected performance, and look for performance issues and solutions.

Governments throughout the world employ monitoring and evaluation to enhance educational outcomes and school systems, and they can be crucial to a comprehensive reform of education. Applying outcomes-based planning and assessment as well as the planning, monitoring, and evaluation cycle to education transformation projects may be beneficial for education leaders at all levels. Educational transformation Plans can gain from monitoring and assessment in several ways, including helping to define and assess process metrics and quality indicators and process measures, assessing progress toward desired educational outcomes, boosting stakeholder engagement and enabling teachers and

institute administrators to create, maintain change in their institutions of learning.

Since every educational system is different, evaluators need to be ready to adjust their evaluation methodology according to the environment and goals of their programs. Monitoring and evaluation should be prioritized for efficient quality delivery as it is evident that neglecting them would negatively impact an organization's ability to succeed.

Types of Monitoring

There are two types of monitoring being used:

1. Internal Monitoring
2. External Monitoring

In recent times, two monitoring systems in the Punjab province's (Pakistan) Department of Education have been implemented.

The PMIU (External Monitoring) and departmental (Internal Monitoring) monitoring are the independent variables. The performance in terms of student attendance and enrollment, teacher attendance, school councils, educational facilities, and general administration make up the dependent variables.

The notion of high-quality education: Especially in objective no. 6, which reads: "enhancing all facets of the academic quality and ensuring outstanding performance of all so that accepted and quantifiable educational results are attained by all, especially in the areas of literacy, math, and essential life skills," the Forum for Education in Dakar hosted in 2000 (UNESCO, 2000). The World Bank (1995, 1999) has acknowledged the significance of quality in educational policy texts. However, as the Independent Evaluation Group of the World Bank (2006) study demonstrates, its fundamental instruction initiatives in growing nations since 1990 have come under fire for being too focused on raising participation rates. The study suggests that children's learning progress is not given enough attention. Just a decade afterward, the Dakar Agenda for Accomplishment, which was endorsed in Senegal at the World Education Forum, elaborated on the idea of educational excellence. Quality was now acknowledged as being of utmost importance, and a list of prerequisites for effective educational programs was created. These included qualified instructors, sufficient resources for learning materials and facilities, a pertinent syllabus, a comfortable environment for learning, as well as a thorough description and evaluation of learning objectives.

Towards Quality Education for All:

A Critical Examination of Global Initiatives and Challenges from EFA to the MDGs

An extended vision for addressing learning requirements was presented during the Global Education for All Conference (EFA) in Johannesburg in 1990. This idea highlighted the need to enhance and evaluate learning accomplishment (UNESCO, 1990). In Dakar, during the 2000 World Education Forum, goal no. 6—which reads, the importance of education was underlined even further by the statement, "enhancing all facets of the academic quality and maintaining perfection of all to ensure approved and quantifiable educational results are achieved by all, especially in the areas of literacy, mathematics, and other vital life abilities." 2000; UNESCO. Numerous nations have seen notable improvements in their rates of school completion since Jomtien. Nevertheless, the quality of education hasn't always improved in tandem with these advancements. It is significantly more difficult to provide "quality education for all" in nations and communities where access to learning is guaranteed. The World Bank (1995, 1999) has acknowledged the significance of quality in educational policy texts. However, as the World Bank Independent Evaluation Group's (2006) study indicates, its fundamental education initiatives in growing nations since 1990 have come under fire for being too focused on raising participation rates. The study suggests that children's learning progress is not given enough attention. Additionally, it implies that developing nations and their allies should reassess their national Fast Track Initiative (FTI) programs, focus on enhancing student learning outcomes, and stress the accomplishment of the Millennium Development Goals (MDGs). Excellent schooling in the context of life skills, literacy, and math, learning outcomes can support increased work output, greater personal incomes, social and economic development, better education, and the

current new generation of novel thoughts, as evidenced by literature (e.g., Towards Quality Education for All: A Critical Examination of Global Initiatives and Challenges from EFA to the MDGs" Towards Quality Education for All: A Critical Examination of Global Initiatives and Challenges from EFA to the MDGs" [This can lead to better teaching practices and ultimately improve academic excellence.](#)

Assurance of Quality and Monitoring: Business and industry were the initial contexts in which the term "quality assurance" was used. These featured easily recognizable goods or artifacts, making it simple to evaluate and guarantee their quality (Kistan, 1999). When the industry became mechanised and humans were relegated to a supporting role on the assembly line, quality assurance was born. Employee disinterest in the products resulted from their lack of control over the final product (Grey, 1987). Inspectors were introduced to help business owners ensure the quality of their products. Their primary objective was to find errors and then implement corrective measures. The phrase "quality assurance" originated from this procedure, which is known as "quality control mechanisms" (Allais, 2009), which guaranteed the production of high-quality goods. Kistan (1999) developed a combined definition of quality assurance in the context of education that aims to incorporate four different pertinent dimensions (see Figure 1). The amalgamated definition's nice feature is that it incorporates both common languages used in everyday practice and all intuitive ideas about quality assurance. The verbs "ensure," "assure," and so forth all essentially mean the same thing or Roel J. Bosker and Vanessa Scherman - 9789463004534 obtained via Brill.com download May 22, 2023, 1:14:54 P.M. through the University of Groningen

Main objectives of assessment and monitoring in educational institutions:

The key aims of monitoring and evaluation in educational institutions are to evaluate the success of instructional policies and plans, detect gaps between planned and achieved results, and ensure compliance between expectations and outcomes. Processes for evaluation and monitoring are crucial in various areas of education including student, teacher, school, and system evaluation, and a framework is essential for efficient policy implementation. Ministry of Education must develop a robust education planning system with a monitoring and evaluation framework, addressing policy challenges such as articulating evaluation, developing competencies, establishing links with classroom practice, and overcoming implementation challenges.

The Process of School Monitoring

2.1. Instruments and Mechanisms

School monitoring employs a range of instruments and mechanisms to assess academic standards. Classroom observations, standardized tests, teacher evaluations, and curriculum audits are common tools used to gather data on teaching and learning processes (Hamilton et al., 2003). These instruments provide insightful observations regarding the efficacy of educational practices, helping educators determine what needs to be improved.

2.2. Stakeholder Involvement

Effective school monitoring often involves multiple stakeholders, including administrators, teachers, students, parents, and policymakers (Kutsyuruba et al., 2016). Collaborative monitoring efforts facilitate a holistic understanding of academic standards and encourage a shared commitment to their promotion (Lieberman & Pointer Mace, 2010). Engaging stakeholders in the monitoring process fosters accountability and transparency in education.

3. Outcomes of School Monitoring

3.1. Improved Teaching Practices

Research consistently demonstrates that school monitoring leads to improvements in teaching practices (Hanushek et al., 2015). By providing teachers with feedback on their performance, monitoring promotes professional development and pedagogical innovation. Effective teaching, aligned with academic standards, enhances student learning outcomes.

3.2. Accountability and Transparency

School monitoring enhances accountability within educational systems. It holds educators and institutions responsible for meeting established standards and encourages transparency in reporting results (Elmore, 2004). The accountability provided by monitoring mechanisms is crucial for maintaining public trust and confidence in education.

3.3. Equitable Access to Quality Education

Monitoring can also address disparities in educational outcomes. By identifying and rectifying inequities in resources, teacher quality, and learning opportunities, monitoring contributes to ensuring that every pupil can access high academic quality schooling (Reardon, 2011). This is particularly relevant in promoting social justice and narrowing achievement gaps.

3.4. Challenges and Considerations

While school monitoring is essential for promoting academic standards, it is not without challenges. Issues such as standardized testing bias, the overemphasis on test scores, and the potential for unintended consequences should be carefully considered (Koretz, 2017). Striking a balance between accountability and supporting professional growth is crucial.

3.5 Administer regular assessment and evaluation methods

There is a noticeable positive influence of external quality monitoring on teaching programs, even though there are conflicts between accountability-led requirements and the improvement of teaching and learning. {Horsburgh, 1997 #1}. Within the framework of education, Kistan (1999) proposed a combined definition of quality control that incorporates four distinct dimensions. This definition aims to capture the multifaceted nature of quality assurance in education. The term amalgamated refers to the combination of intuitive notions and everyday practices related to quality assurance. The verbs used in this context, such as "ensure" and "assure," convey a shared meaning, emphasizing the commitment to maintaining and enhancing the quality of educational processes and outcomes. Overall, the evolution of quality assurance from industrial settings to education reflects a continual effort to uphold and enhance standards in the production of goods and the delivery of education. Naturally, "enhanced" is listed next to "maintained," as it makes sense to raise the caliber of work when it falls short of expectations.

The Significance of Monitoring and Assessment:

Evaluation and monitoring are essential for monitoring and evaluating educational program performance and developing appropriate policies. With increased international funding for education, accurate statistics are needed to track progress and ensure accountability. Reliable and timely data is necessary for making decisions, especially in developing countries. Monitoring data can help adapt strategies to local conditions and increase effectiveness. Most strategies struggle to predict their effectiveness in specific settings, so it's important to monitor any strategy to ensure its effectiveness. According to Koppi-Tessio (2002) and Fitzgerald et al. (2009), M&E systems differ depending on the type, industry, and nation of application. According to Jha et al. (2010), a good Monitoring and Evaluation system should therefore be designed for a particular situation while allowing for creativity and adaptability. Organizations ought to consider other organizations' experiences as inspiration while developing their Monitoring and Evaluation systems

(Briceno, 2010).

As a result, it is essential to understand purpose and application of M&E systems as well as the engagement of stakeholders. According to CARE (2012), M&E has a wide range of audiences, including managers, donors, field employees, partners, policymakers, and program participants. Punjab has developed a robust monitoring system to ensure the program's implementation by the education department. This system monitors progress, identifies problems, and provides continuous feedback. Implementation personnel make use of this data to make required adjustments for improved efficiency and efficacy, ultimately improving the performance of schools.

METHODOLOGY By approach this study was a survey with a descriptive goal. The following protocol was used to carry out the research.

Study Type: Survey and Descriptive

Methodology: Quantitative and Qualitative (QUAN-qual)

Approach: Explanatory Sequential Technique

The study's population included all of chief Executive Education Officers, District Monitoring Officers (DMO), District Education Officers, Head of Secondary School, and SST/PST Teachers, the population also included Monitoring and Evaluation Assistants (MEA) employed in Punjab. The study's population was comprised of five stakeholders. Information was taken from the Punjab government's official website.

Population

There were five stakeholders in the study population specifics as follows:

- 1. Officer for District Monitoring (DMO):** The DMO is in charge of the district-level External System of Monitoring. Thus, the population of all 36 DMOs operating in Punjab was considered.
- 2. Secondary Education Officers (DEOs):** DEO-Secs oversee secondary schools within their district. Because of this, the population includes all 36 DEOs-Secondary.
- 3. Head of Secondary School:** At the school level, the head teacher is the direct supervisor. Consequently, all 4,498 head teachers in Punjab's 4498 government secondary schools who were carrying out their obligations were included in
- 4. Secondary School Teacher:** Having experienced the monitoring system firsthand, secondary school teachers are aware of the actual effectiveness of external monitoring at the level of secondary education. Thus, a population of 25145 secondary school's teachers were included.
- 5. Monitoring and Evaluation Assistant (MEA):** An External Monitoring System field staff. Therefore, the 1,078 MEAs employed in Punjab were counted as part of the population.

In this manner, the Punjab Education Department's overall population was 30,792 (36 DMOs, 36 DEOs_ sec., 4498 head teachers, 25145 secondary school teachers, and 1078 MEAs).

Sampling Framework: To make the sample representative of all the geographical regions it is decided to take the sampling framework. It is decided to take three regions of Punjab: South Punjab, North Punjab, and Central Punjab.

Sampling: A stratified sampling technique was adopted.

- In first stage three sample regions (Central Punjab, South Punjab, and Northern Punjab), were selected from Punjab, and then sample districts were selected from all three regions (Faisalabad, Rahim Yar Khan, and Rawalpindi).
- From each district twenty public secondary schools were selected through stratified sampling technique.

Presentation of research design and instruments

The research design and research instruments of the study were initially presented orally to the instructors and researchers at Rahim Yar Khan's Khawaja Fared University of Engineering and Information Technology's Department of Education, Pakistan, and also to the experts in the field of Monitoring and Evaluation MEAs, and School Principals for validation. Each participant in the presentation received a copy of all the materials. Following the presentation, a question-and-answer session was conducted, which proved helpful in refining the proposal and the instruments. Two

self-developed questionnaires were created in order to determine the efficacy of external monitoring using a Likert scale. one survey questionnaire for Headteachers, SST, and PST teachers and a second for Monitoring and Evaluation Assistants. Semi-structured interview protocol for the Chief Executive Officers, District Education Officer, and DMO was also administered by the researcher. There was also a discussion regarding the domains of External Monitoring and Evaluation in the school secondary schools of Punjab. Three statements dealt with the overall management of schools, two with the supervision of school councils, and five with the monitoring of educational and sanitary facilities. The themes and number of questions associated with these domains were deliberated upon, taking into consideration the study's objectives. The questionnaires initially consisted of 89 items, while the interview had 16 items. However, after the presentation, question-and-answer session, and discussion, the participants recommended reducing the questionnaire to 64 items and the interview to 14 items.

Validity of Instrument: Expert opinion and peer review ensured the validity of the research tool. Following validation, a few adjustments were made to the research instrument's statements. The questionnaire's final draft was used to assess the instrument's dependability. It was determined to be valid for achieving the study's goals.

Reliability:

By estimating the internal consistency of items on data collected for pilot testing using SPSS Version 24, the Cronbach's coefficient Alpha formula was used to determine the reliability of the questionnaire. Cronbach's alpha was found to be 0.83. Therefore, not a single item was removed from the survey. For Questionnaire A, A (used for teachers and the head teacher), the Cronbach Alpha value was estimated as 0.889, and for Questionnaire B (used for MEAs), the

Cronbach Alpha value was calculated as 0.788.

Table: Cronbach Alpha Values

DATA COLLECTION:

The participants' and the institution's prior consent was obtained. In each of the Punjabi districts that were chosen, the researcher personally gathered data from a predetermined sample of the research population. Researcher made personal effort to collect the data, A great effort was made during the first stage in the first round 40% data were collected then again in the second stage saw an even larger accomplishment as it resulted in the collection of 60%, and then in third and final round more than 70% data were collected. The mailing system was also used where it was needed and appropriate. Interviews from the DEO.SEC, CEO, and DMO were conducted by the researcher. This coordinated effort across zones exemplifies the tenacity and fortitude of individuals who are participating in the collection of these very important data points. As we go ahead, it is vital that we build upon these successes and handle any remaining issues in order to guarantee a complete and accurate dataset that can be used for the purposes of analysis and decision-making. Frequency, mean value, percentage, and t-test statistical formulas were used to analyse the gathered data using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 24 software.

ANALYSIS OF DATA: The researcher used SPSS version 22 to generate a data sheet and input data into it to achieve this goal. The data was analyzed using statistical tests and calculations such as the mean score, percentage, and standard deviation. To compare the gender responses and districts t-test and ANOVA were applied

Sorting the average

1. One to two standard deviations below the mean
2. Moderate from 2.00 to 3.00
3. 3 to 5 points above the mean

Findings

Table 4.29 shows that Increasing the use of standardized assessments in the monitoring process leads to improvements in education quality. According to data, 46.2% of respondents agreed with the statement that Increasing the use of standardized assessments in the monitoring process leads to improvements in education quality. while 29.2% strongly agreed, 4.8% of respondents disagreed and 7.1% strongly disagreed whereas 12.8% of respondents were undecided with the statement. Collectively 75.4% (44.97%+43.3%) agreed that Increasing the use of standardized assessments in the monitoring process leads to improvements in education quality. A mean score of 3.86 and a standard deviation of 1.109 supported the statement.

Table 4.29: Would increasing the use of standardized assessments in the monitoring process lead to improvements in education quality?

No	Respondents	Stat	Responses						μ	σ
			SDA	DA	UD	A	SA	Total		
1.	Principal/ Head Teachers	<i>f</i>	0	0	0	3	5	8	4.63	0.52
		%	0	0	0	37.5	62.5	100		
2.	PST	<i>f</i>	0	1	2	25	20	48	4.33	0.66
		%	0	2.1	4.2	52.1	41.6	100		
3.	SST	<i>f</i>	22	14	38	116	66	256	3.74	1.15
		%	8.6	5.5	14.8	45.3	25.8	100		
Total		<i>f</i>	22	15	40	144	91	312	3.86	1.109
		%	7.1	4.8	12.8	46.2	29.2	100		

Table Error! No text of specified style in document.-1 Would increasing the use of standardized assessments in the monitoring process lead to improvements in education quality?

Table 4.30 represented that A monitoring framework can help to identify areas where additional resources are needed, such as teacher training or infrastructure improvements. According to data 33.7% of respondents agreed with the statement that A monitoring framework can help to identify areas where additional resources are needed, such as teacher training or infrastructure improvements, while 49.7% strongly agreed, 4.5% respondents disagreed and 4.5% strongly disagreed whereas 7.7% of respondents were undecided with the statement. Collectively 83.4% (33.7%+49.7%) agreed that A monitoring framework can help to identify areas where additional resources are needed, such as teacher training or infrastructure improvements. A mean score of 4.20 and a standard deviation of 1.059 supported the statement. The main metrics for evaluating the effectiveness of the system are provided by student assessment. Policymakers, the general public, administrators, educators, and parents at the national and local levels can assess how well students are currently performing in relation to student learning objectives as well as the degree to which improvement goals are being realised through the use of assessments of student learning.

Table 4.30: A monitoring framework can help to identify areas where additional resources are needed, such as teacher training or infrastructure improvements.

No	Respondents	Stat	Responses						μ	σ
			SDA	DA	UD	A	SA	Total		
1.	Principal/	<i>f</i>	0	0	0	3	5	8	4.63	0.52

	Head Teachers	%	0	0	0	37.5	62.5	100		
2.	PST	<i>f</i>	0	0	5	17	26	48	4.44	0.68
		%	0	0	10.4	35.4	54.2	100		
3.	SST	<i>f</i>	14	14	19	85	124	256	4.13	1.12
		%	5.5	5.5	7.4	33.2	48.4	100		
	Total	<i>f</i>	14	14	24	105	155	312	4.20	1.059
		%	4.5	4.5	7.7	33.7	49.7	100		

Table Error! No text of specified style in document.-2 A monitoring framework can help to identify areas where additional resources are needed, such as teacher training or infrastructure improvements.

Table 4 represented that Would providing additional resources to struggling schools identified through the monitoring process help to improve education quality? According to data, 52.6% of respondents agreed with the statement that Would provide additional resources to struggling schools identified through the monitoring process helps to improve education quality. while 27.2% strongly agreed, 3.2% of respondents disagreed and 9% strongly disagreed whereas 8% of respondents were undecided with the statement. Collectively 79.8% (52.6%+27.2%) agreed that Providing additional resources to struggling schools identified through the monitoring process helps to improve education quality. A mean score of 3.86 and a standard deviation of 1.128 supported the statement.

Table 4.31: Would providing additional resources to struggling schools identified through the monitoring process help to improve education quality?

No	Respondents	Stat	Responses					μ	σ	
			SDA	DA	UD	A	SA			Total
1.	Principal/ Head Teachers	<i>f</i>	0	0	0	1	7	8	4.88	0.35
		%	0	0	0	12.5	87.5	100		
2.	PST	<i>f</i>	0	1	1	36	10	48	4.15	0.55
		%	0	2.1	2.1	75.0	20.8	100		
3.	SST	<i>f</i>	28	9	24	127	68	256	3.77	1.19
		%	10.9	3.5	9.4	49.6	26.6	100		
	Total	<i>f</i>	28	10	25	164	85	312	3.86	1.128
		%	9.0	3.2	8.0	52.6	27.2	100		

Table Error! No text of specified style in document.-3 Would providing additional resources to struggling schools identified through the monitoring process help to improve education quality?

Table 4.32 represented that Is having a teacher evaluation system that includes student feedback and peer evaluations important to identify strengths and weaknesses in teaching practices and support professional growth? According to data, 42.3% of respondents agreed with the statement that Is having a teacher evaluation system that includes student feedback and peer evaluations important to identify strengths and weaknesses in teaching practices and support professional growth? while 34.9% strongly agreed, 3.5% of respondents disagreed and 8.7% strongly disagreed whereas 10.6% of respondents were undecided with the statement. Collectively 77.2% (34.9%+42.3%) agreed that Is having a teacher evaluation system that includes student feedback and peer evaluations important to identify strengths and weaknesses in teaching practices and support professional growth? A mean score of 3.91 and a standard deviation of 1.171 supported the statement.

Table 4.32: Is having a teacher evaluation system that includes student feedback and peer evaluations important to identify strengths and weaknesses in teaching practices and support professional growth?

No	Respondents	Stat	Responses						μ	σ
			SDA	DA	UD	A	SA	Total		
1.	Principal/ Head Teachers	<i>f</i>	0	0	0	2	6	8	4.75	0.46
		%	0	0	0	25.0	75.0	100		
2.	PST	<i>f</i>	0	1	4	22	21	48	4.31	0.72
		%	0	2.1	8.3	45.8	43.8	100		
3.	SST	<i>f</i>	27	10	29	108	82	256	3.81	1.22
		%	10.5	3.9	11.3	42.2	32.0	100		
Total		<i>f</i>	27	11	33	132	109	312	3.91	1.171
		%	8.7	3.5	10.6	42.3	34.9	100		

Table Error! No text of specified style in document.-4 Is having a teacher evaluation system that includes student feedback and peer evaluations important to identify strengths and weaknesses in teaching practices and support professional growth?

Table 4.33 represented that External monitoring can help identify areas of strength and weakness in education systems, and inform targeted interventions to improve quality. According to data 32.1% of respondents agreed with the statement that External monitoring can help identify areas of strength and weakness in education systems, and inform targeted interventions to improve quality, while 48.1% strongly agreed, 3.5% respondents disagreed and 5.8% strongly disagreed whereas 10.6% of respondents were undecided with the statement. Collectively 80.2% (48.1%+32.1%) agreed that External monitoring can help identify areas of strength and weakness in education systems, and inform targeted interventions to improve quality. A mean score of 3.97 and a standard deviation of 1.044 supported the statement. The main metrics for evaluating the effectiveness of the system are provided by student assessment.

Policymakers, the general public, administrators, educators, and parents at the national and local levels can assess how well students are currently performing in relation to student learning objectives as well as the degree to which improvement goals are being realised through the use of assessments of student learning.

Table 4.33: External monitoring can help identify areas of strength and weakness in education systems, and inform targeted interventions to improve quality.

No	Respondents	Stat	Responses						μ	σ
			SDA	DA	UD	A	SA	Total		
1.	Principal/ Head Teachers	<i>f</i>	0	0	0	5	3	8	4.38	0.5
		%	0	0	0	62.5	37.5	100		
2.	PST	<i>f</i>	0	0	2	30	16	48	4.29	0.5
		%	0	0	4.2	62.5	33.3	100		
3.	SST	<i>f</i>	18	11	31	115	81	256	3.89	1.1
		%	7.0	4.3	12.1	44.92	31.64	100		
Total		<i>f</i>	18	11	33	150	100	312	3.97	1.04
		%	5.8	3.5	10.6	48.1	32.1	100		

Figure Error! No text of specified style in document.-1 External monitoring can help identify areas of strength and

weakness in education systems, and inform targeted interventions to improve quality.

Table 4.34 represented that Increasing collaboration between schools and the monitoring agency would improve education quality? According to data 35.3% of respondents agreed with the statement that Would increased collaboration between schools and the monitoring agency would improve education quality. while 39.4% strongly agreed, 5.4% of respondents disagreed and 6.4% strongly disagreed whereas 13.5% of respondents were undecided with the statement. Collectively 74.7% (35.3%+39.4%) agreed that Would increase collaboration between schools and the monitoring agency would improve education quality. A mean score of 3.96 and a standard deviation of 1.152 supported the statement.

Table 4.34: Would increased collaboration between schools and the monitoring agency improve education quality?

No	Respondents	Stat	Responses						μ	σ
			SDA	DA	UD	A	SA	Total		
1.	Principal/ Head Teachers	<i>f</i>	1	0	0	2	5	8	4.25	1.39
		%	12.5	0	0	25.0	62.5	100		
2.	PST	<i>f</i>	1	2	4	19	22	48	4.23	0.93
		%	2.1	4.2	8.3	39.6	45.8	100		
3.	SST	<i>f</i>	18	15	38	89	96	256	3.89	1.17
		%	7.0	5.9	14.8	34.8	37.5	100		
Total		<i>f</i>	20	17	42	110	123	312	3.96	1.152
		%	6.4	5.4	13.5	35.3	39.4	100		

Table Error! No text of specified style in document.-5 Would increased collaboration between schools and the monitoring agency would improve education quality?

Table 4.35 represented that as a result of performance evaluation and student evaluation quality of education improved. According to data, 39.4% of respondents agreed with the statement that as a result of performance evaluation and student evaluation quality of education improved, while 41% strongly agreed, 2.2% of respondents disagreed and 7.7% strongly disagreed whereas 9.6% of respondents were undecided with the statement. Collectively 80.4% (39.4%+41%) agreed that as a result of performance evaluation and student evaluation quality of education improved. A mean score of 4.04 and a standard deviation of 1.136 supported the statement.

Table 4.35: As a result of performance evaluation and student evaluation quality of education improved.

No	Respondents	Stat	Responses						Mean	SD
			SDA	DA	UD	A	SA	Total		
1	Principal/ Head Teachers	<i>f</i>	0	0	0	3	5	8	μ	σ
		%	0	0	0	37.5	62.5	100		
2.	PST	<i>f</i>	0	1	3	31	13	48	4.17	0.63
		%	0	2.1	6.3	64.5	27.1	100		
3.	SST	<i>f</i>	24	6	27	89	110	256	3.99	1.21
		%	9.4	2.3	10.5	34.8	43.0	100		
Total		<i>f</i>	24	7	30	123	128	312	4.04	1.136
		%	7.7	2.2	9.6	39.4	41.0	100		

Table Error! No text of specified style in document.-6 As a result of performance evaluation and student evaluation quality of education improved.

Table 4.36 represented that as a result of monitoring cells, school performance improved. According to data, 48.1% of respondents agreed with the statement that as a result of monitoring cells, school performance improved, while 31.1% strongly agreed, 2.9% of respondents disagreed and 7.4% strongly disagreed whereas 10.6% of respondents were undecided about the statement. Collectively 79.2% (48.1%+31.1%) agreed that as a result of monitoring cells, school performance improved. A mean score of 3.93 and a standard deviation of 1.093 supported the statement.

Table 4.36: As a result of monitoring cells, school performance improved.

No	Respondents	Stat	Responses						μ	σ
			SDA	DA	UD	A	SA	Total		
1.	Principal/ Head Teachers	<i>f</i>	0	0	0	1	7	8	4.88	0.35
		%	0	0	0	12.5	87.5	100		
2.	PST	<i>f</i>	0	0	2	27	19	48	4.35	0.56
		%	0	0	4.2	56.3	39.5	100		
3.	SST	<i>f</i>	23	9	31	122	71	256	3.81	1.14
		%	9.0	3.5	12.1	47.7	27.7	100		
Total		<i>f</i>	23	9	33	150	97	312	3.93	1.093
		%	7.4	2.9	10.6	48.1	31.1	100		

Table Error! No text of specified style in document.-7 As a result of monitoring cells, school performance improved.

Table 4.40 represented that Would incorporating student and parent feedback into the monitoring process helps to improve the quality of education According to data 48.4% of respondents agreed with the statement that Would incorporating student and parent feedback into the monitoring process helps to improve the quality of education while 24% were strongly agreed, 5.8% respondents were disagreed and 8.7% were strongly disagreed whereas 13.1% of respondents were undecided with the statement. Collectively 83.06% (45.23%+37.83%) agreed that Would incorporate student and parent feedback into the monitoring process helps to improve the quality of education Mean score 3.73 and standard deviation 1.174 supported the statement.

Table 4.40: Would incorporating student and parent feedback into the monitoring process helps to improve the quality of education?

No	Respondents	Stat	Responses						μ	σ
			SDA	DA	UD	A	SA	Total		
1.	Principal/ Head Teachers	<i>f</i>	1	0	0	2	5	8	4.25	1.39
		%	12.5	0	0	25.0	62.5	100		
2.	PST	<i>f</i>	0	0	3	31	14	48	4.23	0.56
		%	0	0	6.3	64.6	29.1	100		
3.	SST	<i>f</i>	26	18	38	118	56	256	3.62	1.19
		%	10.2	7.0	14.8	46.1	21.9	100		
Total		<i>f</i>	27	18	41	151	75	312	3.73	1.147
		%	8.7	5.8	13.1	48.4	24.0	100		

Table Error! No text of specified style in document.-8 Would incorporating student and parent feedback into the monitoring

process helps to improve the quality of education

Table 4.41 represented that External monitoring should be used in conjunction with other strategies to improve the quality of education, such as capacity building, teacher training, and community engagement. According to data 55.1% of respondents agreed with the statement that External monitoring should be used in conjunction with other strategies to improve the quality of education, such as capacity building, teacher training, and community engagement, whereas 22.1% strongly agreed, 4.2% respondents disagreed and 9.3% strongly disagreed whereas 9.3% of respondents were undecided with the statement. Collectively 77.2% (55.1%+22.1%) agreed that External monitoring should be used in conjunction with other strategies to improve the quality of education, such as capacity building, teacher training, and community engagement. Mean score 3.77 and standard deviation 1.125 supported the statement.

Table 4.41: External monitoring should be used in conjunction with other strategies to improve the quality of education, such as capacity building, teacher training, and community engagement.

No	Respondents	Stat	Responses					μ	σ	
			SDA	DA	UD	A	SA			Total
1.	Principal/ Head Teachers	<i>f</i>	0	0	0	3	5	8	4.63	0.52
		%	0	0	0	25.0	75.0	100		
2.	PST	<i>f</i>	0	0	4	37	7	48	4.06	0.48
		%	0	0	8.3	77.1	14.6	100		
3.	SST	<i>f</i>	29	13	25	132	57	256	3.68	1.20
		%	11.3	5.1	9.8	51.6	22.3	100		
Total		<i>f</i>	29	13	29	172	69	312	3.77	1.125
		%	9.3	4.2	9.3	55.1	22.1	100		

Table Error! No text of specified style in document.-9 External monitoring should be used in conjunction with other strategies to improve the quality of education, such as capacity building, teacher training, and community engagement

Table 4.42 represented that Is it important to gather feedback from parents on their child's educational experience to identify areas for improvement and build stronger partnerships between schools and families? According to data, 45.2% of respondents agreed with the statement that Is it important to gather feedback from parents on their child's educational experience to identify areas for improvement and build stronger partnerships between schools and families? whereas 31.1% strongly agreed, 6.1% of respondents disagreed and 3.26% strongly disagreed whereas 6.16% of respondents were undecided with the statement. Collectively 76.3% (45.2%+31.1%) agreed that Is it important to gather feedback from parents on their child's educational experience to identify areas for improvement and build stronger partnerships between schools and families? Mean score 3.85 and standard deviation 1.164 supported the statement.

Table 4.42: Is it important to gather feedback from parents on their child's educational experience to identify areas for improvement and build stronger partnerships between schools and families?

No	Respondents	Stat	Responses					μ	σ	
			SDA	DA	UD	A	SA			Total
1.	Principal/ Head Teachers	<i>f</i>	0	0	0	2	6	8	4.75	0.46
		%	0	0	0	25.0	75.0	100		
2.	PST	<i>f</i>	0	0	4	27	17	48	4.27	0.61
		%	0	0	8.3	56.3	35.4	100		
3.	SST	<i>f</i>	25	19	26	112	74	256	3.74	1.22
		%	9.8	7.4	10.2	43.8	28.9	100		
Total		<i>f</i>	25	19	30	141	97	312	3.85	1.16
		%	9.3	4.2	9.3	55.1	22.1	100		

% 8.0 6.1 9.6 45.2 31.1 100

Table Error! No text of specified style in document.-10 Is it important to gather feedback from parents on their child's educational experience to identify areas for improvement and build stronger partnerships between schools and families?

Domain table analysis

Quality of Education

Questions	M	Σ
Would increasing the use of standardized assessments in the monitoring process lead to improvements in education quality?	3.74	1.156
A monitoring framework can help to identify areas where additional resources are needed, such as teacher training or infrastructure improvements.	4.14	1.121
Would providing additional resources to struggling schools identified through the monitoring process help to improve education quality?	3.77	1.199
Is having a teacher evaluation system that includes student feedback and peer evaluations important to identify strengths and weaknesses in teaching practices and support professional growth?	3.81	1.229
External monitoring can help identify areas of strength and weakness in education systems, and inform targeted interventions to improve quality.	3.9	1.112
Would increased collaboration between schools and the monitoring agency improve education quality?	3.9	1.177
As a result of performance evaluation and student evaluation quality of education improved.	4	1.216
As a result of monitoring cells, school performance improved.	3.82	1.149
Total	3.88	1.169

Table Error! No text of specified style in document.-11 Quality of Education

This table provides an overview of different domains related to Quality Education. Looking at the domains, the monitoring process leads to improvements in education quality and the monitoring framework can help to identify areas where additional resources are needed having mean values of 3.74 and 4.14 and standard deviations of 1.156 and 1.121 respectively in the Quality Education domain table. Further, this table shows the mean and standard values of providing additional resources to struggling schools identified through the monitoring process helps to improve education quality and the student feedback and peer evaluations important to identify strengths and weaknesses in teaching practices and Would increase collaboration between schools and the monitoring agency would improve education quality? Both have 3.9 mean values and 1.112 and 1.177 standard deviations accordingly. the average ratings for all the domains combined are 3.97, suggesting a generally positive perception of the external Monitoring and Evaluation system in schools. However, it is important to consider that these findings are based on the responses of the participants and may represent their subjective opinions about the different domains of Quality education.

Conclusion:

As a result, M&E becomes an essential component of the entire educational system since it guarantees the prompt detection and resolution of issues with projects, policies, and programmes related to education. Additionally, it facilitates the assessment of the project, policy, or program's applicability, efficacy, efficiency, impact, and sustainability. Majority of respondent agreed with the statement “Would increasing the use of standardized assessments in the monitoring

process lead to improvements in education quality?”. While some of respondents strongly agreed, very few respondents disagreed and few strongly disagreed, whereas very few of respondent agreed that” Would increasing the use of standardized assessments in the monitoring process lead to improvements in education quality?”. Majority of respondent agreed with the statement “A monitoring framework can help to identify areas where additional resources are needed, such as teacher training or infrastructure improvements”. While some of respondents strongly agreed, very few respondents disagreed and few strongly disagreed, whereas very few of respondent agreed that” A monitoring framework can help to identify areas where additional resources are needed, such as teacher training or infrastructure improvements”. Majority of respondent agreed with the statement “Would provide additional resources to struggling schools identified through the monitoring process help to improve education quality?”. While some of respondents strongly agreed, very few respondents disagreed and few strongly disagreed, whereas very few of respondent agreed that” Would provide additional resources to struggling schools identified through the monitoring process help to improve education quality?”. Majority of respondent agreed with the statement “Is having a teacher evaluation system that includes student feedback and peer evaluations important to identify strengths and weaknesses in teaching practices and support professional growth?”. While some of respondents strongly agreed, very few respondents disagreed and few strongly disagreed, whereas very few respondents agreed that” having a teacher evaluation system that includes student feedback and peer evaluations important to identify strengths and weaknesses in teaching practices and support professional growth?”. The majority of respondents agreed with the statement “External monitoring can help identify areas of strength and weakness in education systems, and inform targeted interventions to improve quality”. While some of the respondents strongly agreed, very few respondents disagreed and few strongly disagreed, whereas very few respondents agreed that” External monitoring can help identify areas of strength and weakness in education systems, and inform targeted interventions to improve quality”. The majority of respondents agreed with the statement “ Would increasing collaboration between schools and the monitoring agency would improve education quality?”. While some of the respondents strongly agreed, very few respondents disagreed and few strongly disagreed, whereas very few of respondent agreed that” Would increase collaboration between schools and the monitoring agency would improve education quality?”. The majority of respondents agreed with the statement “As a result of performance evaluation and student evaluation quality of education improved”. While some of the respondents strongly agreed, very few respondents disagreed and few strongly disagreed, whereas very few respondents agreed that” As a result of performance evaluation and student evaluation quality of education improved”. The majority of respondents agreed with the statement “As a result of monitoring cells, school performance improved”. While some of the respondents strongly agreed, very few respondents disagreed and few strongly disagreed, whereas very few respondents agreed that” As a result of monitoring cells, school performance improved”.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS: External monitoring is an important aspect of ensuring academic quality in secondary schools. According to a chapter in the book “Monitoring the Quality of Education in Schools” by Vanessa Scherman and Roel J. Bosker, external monitoring can help assure quality in education. The chapter highlights that external monitoring can be used to evaluate the effectiveness of schools and teachers, and to identify areas for improvement.

Effective monitoring encourages collaboration and generates positive and supportive professional discussion². It can also empower teachers to take personal responsibility for improving teaching and learning.

Good supervision fosters teamwork and produces constructive and encouraging professional dialogue². It can also provide educators the confidence to take personal accountability for enhancing instruction and learning.

Numerous factors suggested that there were issues with the community as well as the students, given the high level of student absenteeism. Research indicates that students with higher absentee rates tend to have trouble academically or socially. According to a study by Baker and Jansen (2000), students who perform poorly academically and on tests tend

to miss class. More truancy may result if the high absenteeism rate is maintained. Jansen and Baker (2000). Research has demonstrated that a substantial increase in student absences results in a significant loss of learning and instructional time (Mayer & Mitchell, 1993).

One of the main losses students experience when absenteeism rates rise is that they fall behind in their coursework; however, at this point, teachers must make accommodations for the students who are discovered to be absent from class. It is a fact that absenteeism has numerous ramifications outside of the classroom. Due to their lack of focus on their studies, these students drop out of schools with high absentee rates and do not make up for their lost learning (Mayer & Mitchell, 1993).

Poor student enrollment and absenteeism rates are just two of the many issues plaguing Pakistan's education sector and contributing to its inefficiency. One of the most important monthly metrics for which PMIU must gather data is student attendance. A significant obstacle to reaching goals in the elementary and secondary education sectors is the low attendance rate of students. Male students' low attendance rates present a significant challenge, but female students' low attendance has proven to be even more problematic.

Any school management team can improve teaching, learning, planning, and resource allocation by utilizing M&E best practices. They can also better demonstrate results to key stakeholders as part of the school's accountability.

ALAM, S. Evaluation of Punjab's Government Schools Monitoring Programme.

Recommendation: Since the quality of teachers' instruction depends on the feedback provided by the monitoring staff, a lack of sincerity among that staff has an impact on the entire school. For this reason, a secondary school can install an autonomous monitoring and evaluation system so that teachers can receive regular feedback on their instruction and enhance it.

Teachers will be sincerer and improve in their teaching when there are regular monitoring results in lesson plans, classroom supplies, the use of multiple intelligences, home visits from students, and regular evaluation of students' progress will all be used to increase students' sincerity and enthusiasm in learning. It will ultimately result in the impact of students receiving a high-quality education.

Ahmed, Z., Alam, R., & Akter, S. A. (2015). Ahmed, Farid, and Nicholas P. Low. 'Environmental Justice Dialogues and the Struggle for Human Dignity in the Deciduous Forest of Bangladesh'. *Journal of Political Ecology* 27, no. 1 (2020): 300–16. Ahmed, Imdad Ali. 'Elephants in Medieval Assam'. *Proceedings of the Indian History Congress* 76 (2015): 264–70. *Sciences (Geologische Rundschau)*, 104(5), 1235-51.

We used techniques like literature reviews, semi-structured interviews, and survey questionnaires. 380 participants in total answered the survey, including administrators, decision-makers, and school personnel. The findings show that while the department has a detailed monitoring and evaluation system in place, there are still certain problems that need to be fixed to move forward. Some limitations encompass the restricted utilisation of data in decision-making, insufficient resources, and insufficient training of personnel. Another illustration is the limited application of data. Concerns concerning the system's efficacy in raising student academic achievement have also been voiced by several groups. The results have significant implications for education theory and practice as a discipline. To raise the general caliber of the monitoring and evaluation processes that are conducted, it has been suggested that the department allocate more funds to employee training and capacity building. This would be carried out to improve the monitoring's general quality and this would be done to enhance the overall quality of the monitoring and evaluation procedures that are carried out. The results need to be interpreted in a way that is more rigorous and data-driven, with the major aim being the identification of areas that need improvement and the creation of particular solutions. In order to accomplish this goal, it may be necessary to make use of more sophisticated data analysis tools and processes, in addition to increasing the amount of collaboration that occurs among the numerous stakeholders in the education system. It is also extremely important to address the underlying issues that contribute to poor results for kids, such as poverty, inequality, and inadequate infrastructure. This is very important to improve student's learning outcomes. Because of this, the results for

the children will be improved. As a result of this, it is possible that it will be essential to adopt a more comprehensive approach, one that involves partnering with other government agencies and community organizations, in order to address these more widespread social and economic challenges. In the end, enhancing educational results for children will require continuous effort and commitment over a protracted period of time. If, on the other hand, we confront these significant challenges head-on, we will be able to make significant headway toward constructing a system of education that is more effective and equitable for all children. A comparison of these findings with those of prior studies reveals that the challenges that our educational system must solve are not brand new, but they are growing more complicated and rooted in the nature of the challenges themselves. It has been shown that there is a significant disparity in academic success among students who come from different socioeconomic backgrounds. This has been proven to have a significant impact on the results of the kids' education. This is one of the most important obstacles to overcome. In addition, the increasing variety of our student population presents new challenges for educators, who must overcome cultural barriers as well as language obstacles in order to ensure that all children have access to an education that is of an adequate standard of quality. A plan that employs many approaches will be necessary if we are to be successful in overcoming these challenges. This plan should include targeted interventions for children who are seen as being at risk, better support for educators and schools in areas with a high degree of need, and increased investment in early childhood education programs. It will be required for governmental agencies, community organizations, and educational institutions to work together in order to design a plan that is more all-encompassing and comprehensive for solving these challenges. This can only be accomplished through collaboration. If we use a comprehensive approach that recognizes the connection between social and economic factors and educational successes, we may start to make significant progress toward the objective of establishing an education system that is more equitable and successful for all of the nation's children

Some of the policy and practice implications that have been derived from this study include an increased focus on the need for additional funding and resources for schools situated in low-income areas, in addition, policy should emphasize on hiring and maintaining highly qualified teachers, particularly in locations where there is a current shortage of instructors. In addition to this, the techniques that are used to evaluate pupils need to be more flexible so that they can accommodate students who have a variety of approaches to learning and degrees of aptitude. accommodate students who have a variety of approaches to learning and degrees of aptitude. With the help of these initiatives, we will be able to create an educational system that is more equal and effective and that provides all students with the resources they need to fulfill their full potential.

Researchers like Amin, R. U., & Soomro, K. A. (2021) are among them. Naidoo, L., Bipath, K., and 2021. Andrieu, N., and Bonilla Findji, O. (2019); Ahmad, S.; Parveen, Z.; and Yousaf, F. (2022). P. Bartle (2010). conducted investigations into the external monitoring system's variables and challenges. It is widely acknowledged that an organization's ability to perform better depends on its available resources. Resources needed by schools range from monetary to human to technological to instructional. Results showed that 55.1% of respondents agreed with the statement that external monitoring should be used in conjunction with other strategies to improve the quality of education, such as capacity building, teacher training, and community engagement. However, only 22.1% strongly agreed with the statement; 4.2% disagreed; 9.3% strongly disagreed; and 9.3% were unsure. Collectively, 77.2% (55.1% + 22.1%) were in favor of combining external monitoring with other approaches to raising educational standards, such as capacity building, teacher preparation, and community involvement. The proposition was supported by a mean score of 3.77 and a standard deviation of 1.125 (Table 4.41).

Amir, S., Sharif, N., & Khan, R. A. (2020). Conducted research and revealed that Pakistan's current educational system is thought to be insufficiently responsive to the demand for high-quality education. Many issues are associated with how teaching and learning are organized. Any strategy that is developed to enhance Pakistan's current educational system must take these challenges and concerns into account. Results showed that 55.1% of respondents agreed with the statement that External monitoring should be used in conjunction with other strategies to improve the quality of education, such as capacity building, teacher training, and community engagement, whereas 22.1% strongly agreed, 4.2% respondents disagreed and 9.3% strongly disagreed whereas 9.3% of respondents were undecided with the statement. Collectively 77.2% (55.1%+22.1%) agreed that External monitoring should be used in conjunction with other strategies to improve the quality of education, such as capacity building, teacher training, and community engagement.

A mean score of 3.77 and a standard deviation of 1.125 supported the statement (Table 4.41).

The discussion also focuses on how an effective monitoring structure may promote responsibility, openness, and confidence in the educational system. According to the vast majority of research participants, a monitoring framework enables the government to identify areas for development and effectively manage resources. Similarly, this, it is believed to be essential to establish a teacher evaluation system that considers feedback from peers and students to identify teaching practices' strengths and weaknesses and to support professional development.

It was discovered that External Monitoring performs better than average overall. In terms of facilities provided to schools, active participation by school councils, and general administration in Punjab secondary schools, external monitoring is found to be effective. These results are consistent with the study that Muneer, Naseem, Aneesa, and Shazia (2011) conducted. It is discovered that, in comparison to the opinions of other stakeholders, DMOs are relatively more in favour of External Monitoring's performance with regard to school councils. Given that MEA and DMO are External Monitoring System stakeholders, it could be the result of personal biases on the part of the stakeholder. Naturally, average people also like their department or system. As a result, DMOs and MEAs are found to support their system. The opinions of all stakeholders regarding the effectiveness of the External Monitoring System in terms of keeping an eye on educational facilities do not significantly differ from one another. On the other hand, it is found that the opinions of DMOs are more in favor of External Monitoring in terms of monitoring of general administration than the opinions of other stakeholders. It was also found by Muneer, Naseem, Aneesa, and Shazia (2011). The findings of Mahmood, Anwar, and Khan (2012) also support this point of view. The findings of Mehmood et.al (2021) also support these results.

RECOMMENDATIONS

1. Officers in the education department may receive managerial training at an education service academy that is set up. In order to provide education officers with up-to-date knowledge and skills of educational management and leadership of the global arena, there may be a six-month training programme for newly appointed officers of the education department and a one-month training programme every year. Along with other management tasks like organising, budgeting, controlling, planning, and directing, etc., monitoring training may be prioritized.

2. A separate wing for monitoring may be established consisting of fresh appointments or retired educational officers. DEO monitoring may be appointed in each district of Punjab assisted by field staff to visit schools and maintain records. The Chief Minister Monitoring Force is the current name of the external monitoring programme in Punjab. They are ineffective and irrelevant in the education department, and they have a lot of other departments to oversee, such as hospitals. Due to their incapacity to oversee the curriculum, lesson planning, classroom administration, etc. They can't function well therefore, aside from paperwork.

The monitoring system ought to be compliant with the MDGs pertaining to education, including granting boys' and girls' equal access to schools and raising the standard of instruction for all pupils. To enable the monitoring system to monitor the advancement of the MDGs pertaining to education, indicators need to be set up. Indicators pertaining to education can be established to monitor various aspects such as student achievement, literacy rates, and enrollment rates. Tracking progress toward the education-related MDGs requires frequent data collection using specified indicators, which should be done through the monitoring system. There are times when the shortcomings of monitoring and evaluation are brought to light, and while donor organisations have offered advice on how to improve these systems through training, not much has actually changed. To quickly address the poor performance of the monitoring and assessment systems, investigations are necessary.

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